

A STUDY OF THE IMPORTANCE OF ALLIANCE BETWEEN CULTURE AND LITERATURE

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Abstract

The research paper is a modest attempt for tracing the relationship shared between Culture and Literature. Literature is one such medium, through which one culture or subculture can codify and transfer their cultural values and traditions from one generation to the next. Culture, undoubtedly is a wider concept than literature. Thus, in the teaching of culture, literature plays different roles, such as: it serves as a basis for the study and mediation of cultural phenomena. There is no literature in the world which can be put away from culture as literature always depicts the experience of life.

No literature is separate from culture; literature and culture are blended together. Literature is the off shoot of the real experiences. I have tried to depict the relationship between culture and literature.

Key words: Culture, Anarchy, Materialism, Imperialism, Orientalism,

Introduction

Literature holds the ability of describing anything, from creative writing to more technical or scientific works, but the term literature is widely used to define the works of creative imagination, which includes poetry, drama, fiction and non-fiction. The word literature originates from the Latin word littera, which means ‘acquaintance with letters.’ Essentially, literature is one such medium, through which one culture or subculture can codify and transfer their cultural values and traditions from one generation to the next. Hence, the question, ‘What is literature?’ becomes important, due to this reason. Literature not only represents a language or people, but it also introduces the readers to the new worlds of experiences. For instance, it helps us to reflect upon our own preconceptions, values and ethics. One discovers meaning in literature by looking at what the author says and how he/she says it. Literature is important to us, because it speaks to us, it is universal and above all, it affects us.

Relevance of Culture to Literature

Culture, undoubtedly is a wider concept than literature. So in this context, it will be understood well in terms of its relationship with literature, as the combination between literature and culture is a significant one. Thus, in the teaching of culture, literature plays different roles, such

as: it serves as a basis for the study and mediation of cultural phenomena. Culture distinguishes human beings from animals. It refers to music, dance, literature, architecture and other creative activities; suggests tradition and heritage; denotes civilization and indicates the commonly shared ideas and practices of a group of people.

The disciplines of language, literature and cultural studies are linked together, because they tend to focus on the relationship between language and literature in a certain cultural environment. Language studies or linguistics is that science, which tackles language from the perspective of structure, form, meaning and context. While literature is the art of written composition divided in poetry, prose and theater. The complex disciplines of language, literature and cultural studies aims at enabling the students to build a deep understanding of a culture based on the language and literature of that culture. Literature has been considered a very powerful tool, as it offers insight into the building elements of a culture, the particular characteristics of a society or social group in terms of spirituality, intellect, emotion and physical environment. The fascinating discipline, like literature, helps us to understand the value and cultural diversity of the human society which is becoming more globalized day by day. By being aware of various cultures, we not only preserve the valuable artifacts and manifestations of a variety of cultures, but we are also able to communicate and cooperate better with the people belonging from various cultural backgrounds.

Literature Review

The very term ‘culture’ has a unique aspect, which is its ambiguity, because some understand culture in terms of social behaviour, whereas for some poetry, dance and music constitute culture. One of the oldest definition of culture was given by the British anthropologist, Sir E.B. Taylor (1832- 1917) in the opening lines of his book, named as, *Primitive Cultures* (1871), where he defined the term culture as ‘that complex whole which includes knowledge, belief, art, morals, laws, customs and the other capabilities and habits acquired by man as a member of a society.’

In order to get a better understanding of the term culture, we can even consider various other definitions of culture. For instance, Margaret Mead (1901- 78), an American anthropologist defined culture as ‘the learned behaviour of a society or a sub group.’ Whereas Clifford Geertz, Professor of Social Science at Princeton University was of the view that ‘culture is simply the ensemble of stories we tell ourselves about ourselves.’ In a way it will not be wrong to say that, culture seems to be almost everything and cultural studies is the study of almost everything. There is as such no ‘corrective’ or ‘definitive’ meaning attached to the term culture. Indeed, the study of culture has no origins.

The English critic, named Raymond Williams in his work *Keywords* gives a detailed account of the word culture. According to Raymond Williams (1981, 1983) ‘culture is one of the two or three most complicated words in English language.’ By the end of the eighteenth century, the

term culture was used as a synonym for the term civilization. This eventually gave rise to the idea of a cultivated or cultured person. To be civilized or cultured meant to be well-mannered; to know how to appreciate art, music and literature. We come across a similar use of the term even today. In the nineteenth century a more anthropological definition of culture came into existence where culture was understood as ‘a whole and a distinctive way of life whether of a person, a group, a period or of humanity in general.’

The nineteenth century, English writer Matthew Arnold acquired an iconic status within the narrative of cultural studies. He described culture as ‘the best that has been thought and said in the world.’ Arnold in his work *Culture and Anarchy* defined culture ‘as a refined state, which is opposite to anarchy, where there is utter chaos and public protests for rights.’ According to Arnold there was a kind of elitism associated to the term culture and the critical importance ascribed to the term culture is a later twentieth century product. Therefore, it has no ancient forefathers.

Raymond Williams was one of the foremost Marxist thinkers in the second half of the twentieth century, who did an extensive study on the British culture. In the essay “A Hundred Years of Culture and Anarchy” from his book *Culture and Materialism*, Raymond Williams argues, how Arnold tries to define culture in opposition to what Arnold identifies as Anarchy. The British working class men demanded right to vote, this campaign for right to vote was headed by the Reform League, which decided to conduct a meeting at Hyde Park on July 23, 1866. 60,000 workers gathered outside the Hyde Park on the due date of meeting, but they could not enter the park, as the Home Secretary had ordered the police to lock the gates of the park because the royal authorities believed that the parks were meant for recreation, not for mass demonstration, which were a form of nuisance. After this incident, people took down railings, flowerbeds were trampled and stones were thrown at large houses, all this was done in order to get an answer as to whether the portions of the Hyde Park belonged to a class or to all the people.

Hyde Park was in Arnold’s mind when he gave the first lecture which was related to his work named *Culture and Anarchy*. He included Hyde Park protest in which the underline demand was right to vote, under anarchy. Arnold’s proposition of culture depends on an opposition to anarchy. In his book *Culture and Anarchy*, he is not talking about the defeat of the bill, which demanded right to vote, but is laying emphasis on the protest which took place in the Hyde Park. According to Raymond Williams, Arnold’s idea of culture is a problematic one, as his concept of culture is built upon a fragile binary and any concept, which is built upon a binary, is considered to be weak. Raymond Williams recognized culture as something, which is familiar to the people and this is considered to be a demerit because we all consider only the familiar things to be as culture. Thus, in this way, we oppose unfamiliar things and dismiss new ideas by not considering them as standard.

Edward Said, a Palestinian American literary theorist, has expressed his view on culture in his book *Culture and Imperialism* where he referred to culture as ‘the instrument of imperialism’. Said emphasized on the fact that, ‘it is necessary to know the importance of culture, in order to realize the power of imperialism. Said’s definition and interpretation of culture is very broad: He writes: ‘Culture means, all those practices like the arts of description, communication, and representation, that have relative autonomy from the economic, social, and political realms and that often exist in aesthetic forms, one of whose principal aim is pleasure.’ In this regard, Edward Said’s view of culture is somewhat different from Raymond William’s definition of culture as ‘a whole way of life’ (1958). Whereas in Said analysis, culture is indeed the power which changes the views of the colonised people in the world, without the coloniser needing to resort to full-grown military control. It is culture that provides the ethical power, which enabled the British to become the unquestionable ruler of India for nearly two centuries. However, Said focuses on "the politics of blame" approach, including condemning and rejecting the coloniser and blaming the colonised/victims, as a strategy of resistance. He says he has not ‘completely worked on the theory of connection between literature and culture on the one hand, and imperialism on the other’; he just hopes to discover connections between them. He says it is useful to do this because ‘by looking at culture and imperialism carefully, we shall see that we can profitably draw those connections that can enrich and sharpen our reading of major cultural texts.’

Orientalism by Edward Said is a canonical text of cultural studies in which he has challenged the concept of orientalism or the difference between east and west, as he puts it. He says that with the start of European colonization the Europeans came in contact with the lesser developed countries of the east. They found their (east) civilization and culture very exotic, and established the science of orientalism, which was the study of the orients or the people from the exotic civilization.

Conclusion

I believe it is necessary to relate literature and culture because we live in segregated neighborhoods, and our initial acquaintance with other cultures takes place with the help of movies, books and other media. Moreover, knowledge of other culture proves to be beneficial in building healthy relationships with the people coming from different cultural backgrounds.

Literature is one such domain which portrays several types of diversity, such as gender, culture, racial background, language and physical as well as mental abilities. Literature is that area of study, which represents various cultural groups, for instance, literature reflects the multitude of cultural groups within the U.S. as well as those ethnic and regional groups whose cultures historically have been less represented than the European cultures. Moreover, literature has widened its area by representing the ‘parallel cultures’, a phrase coined by Virginia Hamilton, in the present scenario, many minority cultures are no longer numerically in the minority, so the phrase ‘parallel cultures’ refers to some cultures being parallel to the main stream culture:

Asian, Afro- American, Native American and Hispanic. No literature is created in a vacuum, it always comes from culture.

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